

Co-ordination Compounds of Rhodium (III) with Biguanide

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Rhodium (III) forms with biguanide inner metallic complex compounds like cobalt (III). Rhodium tris-biguanidinium sulphate, chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrate, and thiosulphate have been prepared and their properties studied. The complex salts have a very faint cream colour and are diamagnetic with octahedral d^2sp^3 bonding. The rhodium complexes are slightly more stable than the corresponding cobalt complexes, as has been inferred from thermal analysis.

Very few inner metallic complexes of rhodium are known. Complex compounds of rhodium (III) with dimethylglyoxime were investigated by Fedorov (*Chem. Abs.*, 1939, 33, 2060) and by Dwyer and Nyholm (*ibid.*, 1945, 39, 1114). These workers also obtained an inner metallic compound with ethylenediamine bis-salicylaldehyde (*ibid.*, 1946, 40, 3994). Recently, Haines and Ryan (*Canad. J. Res.*, 1949, 27B, 72) have prepared a few inner metallic complexes with thio-ligands, 2-mercaptobenzoxazole, 2-mercaptobenzothiazole, etc.

Biguanide ($C_2H_7N_5$) forms very stable inner metallic complexes with copper, chromium, manganese, cobalt, nickel, and palladium (Rây *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1937, 14, 670; 1938, 15, 347, 353, 633; 1939, 16, 617, 621, et seq). The complexes of Co(III) (Rây *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, p. 621) are deeply coloured, very stable and these exhibit interesting stereochemical properties. In view of the close similarity in properties of hexaco-ordinated rhodium (III) amines and ethylenediamine complexes with the corresponding cobalt (III) complexes, it was considered desirable to study the complexes of rhodium (III) with biguanide.

Rhodium tris-biguanide complexes closely resemble the corresponding cobaltic compounds and can be represented by the general formula $[Rh(BigH^+)_3] X_3$, where X is a univalent anion or its equivalent acid radical and $BigH^+$ represents a molecule of biguanide, $C_2H_7N_5$. No complex rhodium tris-biguanidinium base could, however, be obtained in a pure state like the cobaltic tris-biguanidinium dihydrate or cobaltic tris-biguanidine.

The constitution of the rhodium tris-biguanide complexes may be represented like those of the cobalt complexes. The central rhodium atom forms a neutral inner metallic complex by co-ordinating with the three bidentate biguanide molecules, the cationic character of which is due solely to the free amino groups of the biguanide molecules. The complexes are diamagnetic and hence octahedral with d^2sp^3 bonding. The above configuration has been justified by resolution into optically active modifications like those of the cobaltic tris-biguanide complexes. The complex has been resolved by forming diastereoisomers with *d*-tartrate, a full account of which will be reported later.

Rhodium tris-biguanidinium salts are either colorless or show a faint creamish tint in contrast to the corresponding deeply coloured cobaltic complexes. These are similar in other physical and chemical properties. The sulphates and thiosulphates are slightly soluble while the halides and nitrates are fairly soluble. The rhodium complexes are, however, much less soluble than the corresponding cobaltic complexes. These ionise completely in aqueous solution and are fairly stable, there being little hydrolysis even on boiling. Dilute acids cause decomposition of the complex on heating, but have very little effect in the cold.

Thermolysis curves of the rhodium and cobaltic tris-biguanide complexes are similar, but the rhodium complex appears to be slightly more stable than the cobalt complex. In the case of the complex sulphates, both start losing water of crystallisation at about 70° and become anhydrous at about 160°. The decomposition of the complex starts at 260° in the case of cobalt while the rhodium complex starts decomposing at 280°. In both the cases the decomposition is complete by 650°. From the weight of the residue it is presumed that in both the cases these are finally converted into their oxides (Rh_2O_3 and Co_2O_3).

EXPERIMENTAL

Rhodium Tris-biguanidinium Sulphate.—Biguanide sulphate (0.678 g.) was dissolved in aqueous NaOH (0.12 g.), filtered, and the filtrate was added to a solution of $\text{RhCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.209 g.) in water (10 c.c.). A brownish red colloidal precipitate of rhodium hydroxide separated slowly. This was filtered after keeping overnight and the filtrate was refluxed for about 2 hours when the colour of the solution faded to pale yellow. On cooling needle shaped, silky, very light cream crystals separated. The crystals were purified by recrystallisation from boiling water, washed with cold water, and dried in air. The yield was about 0.2 g. {Found : C, 11.72; H, 4.7; N, 34.46; Rh, 16.50; SO_4 , 23.28; H_2O , 9.37. $[\text{Rh}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2 (\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires C, 11.74; H, 4.63; N, 34.31; Rh, 16.81; SO_4 , 23.53; H_2O , 10.03%}. The substance is diamagnetic. The complex is slightly soluble in cold water and in organic solvents. Dilute acids and alkalis decompose it on boiling. Like its cobaltic analogue, it crystallises with seven molecules of water. The salt becomes anhydrous at 160°, but rapidly absorbs moisture.

Rhodium tris-biguanidinium chloride was obtained by metathesis of the complex sulphate with barium chloride. After removal of BaSO_4 and concentration of the filtrate, the complex chloride separated as light cream, fine crystals. It is soluble in water, decomposes on boiling with dilute acids and alkalis, and is diamagnetic. {Found : Rh, 20.08; Cl, 20.48. $[\text{Rh}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] \text{Cl}_3$ requires Rh, 20.08; Cl, 20.76%}.

Rhodium tris-biguanidinium bromide and iodide were prepared by double decomposition of the chloride with KBr and KI respectively. Their properties are similar to those of the chloride. {Found : Rh, 15.99; Br, 37.8. $[\text{Rh}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] \text{Br}_3$ requires Rh, 15.94; Br, 37.1%}. {Found : Rh, 13.30; I, 49.4. $[\text{Rh}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] \text{I}_3$ requires Rh, 13.07; I, 48.4%}.

Rhodium tris-biguanidinium nitrate was also obtained by metathesis of the sulphate with barium nitrate. The filtrate on evaporation to dryness deposited a light cream complex nitrate. It is fairly soluble in water. On boiling with water it undergoes slight hydrolysis. {Found : Rh, 17.54; N, 42.84; NO_3 , 30.98. $[\text{Rh}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] (\text{NO}_3)_3$ requires Rh, 17.38; N, 42.57; NO_3 , 31.4%}.

TABLE I

Equivalent conductance at 28°.

V (dilution)	..	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Λ_v	..	102.7	109.3	117.6	128.0	134.9	138.9
Λ_{∞}	..	140.4	137.7	139.2	144.6	147.3	147.9
Mean Λ_{∞} =		144.3					

Valency of the complex ion according to Ostwald-Walden's rule is given by $(\Lambda_{1024} - \Lambda_{22})/10$ and works out to 3.6. The value is slightly high, presumably due to hydrolysis. The results compare well with those of cobaltic tris-biguanidinium chloride obtained by Rây *et al.* (*loc. cit.*, p. 621). The ionic conductance of the $[\text{Rh}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]^{3+}$ is $3 \times (135.6 - 71.5) = 192.3$ (after temperature correction at 25°). The value for the $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]^{3+}$, as calculated from the data of Rây *et al.*, is $3 \times (138.5 - 76.3) = 186.6$ (at 25°).

Rhodium Tris-biguanidinium Thiosulphate.—When an aqueous solution of the complex nitrate was treated with sodium thiosulphate, a silky, white, crystalline precipitate of the complex thiosulphate was obtained. It was recrystallised from hot water, washed with cold water, and dried in air. The substance becomes anhydrous at 120°; the anhydrous compound is stable in air. {Found: Rh, 16.70; S, 15.02; H₂O, 8.60. $[\text{Rh}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] 1.5\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Rh, 16.39; S, 15.29; H₂O, 8.26%}.

Attempts to obtain the complex base from the complex sulphate by metathesis with baryta failed. A light yellow solid was obtained which always contained some carbonate.

Thermal analyses were made in a Stanton thermo balance with an overall heating rate of 4° per minute with a charge of about 250 mg.

Thanks are due to the Patna University for granting a scholarship to A. I. P. Sinha and to Dr. J. N. Chatterjea for micro carbon-hydrogen analysis.

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Received November 17, 1960.